

netWorked Youth Research for Empowerment in the Digital society

Grant Agreement number: 727066

First Cycle Activity Toolkit

WP6.1

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1. Introduction

WP6 focuses on the second part of the WYRED cycle (García-Peñalvo, 2016; 2017a; García-Peñalvo & Kearney, 2016), where the consortium facilitates a wide range of exploratory activities, in which groups of young people, internationally or locally, investigate and examine issues that concern them in digital society. The range of actions envisaged includes research projects, where a social issue is addressed and solutions are explored and discussed, surfacing attitudes and understandings are highlighted through reflection in the process; creative projects, making use among others of video, theatre, web publishing, comics, music, art, various events etc., to express attitudes and understanding through the chosen medium; journalistic approaches, to observe, document, record and comment on social phenomena, either online or offline, and to produce documentary outputs in different media; action research and ethnographic projects, in which participants explore their own perceptions in their day-to-day lives, e.g. through journals or video blogging; solidarity projects, where a specific problem is identified and practical solutions are implemented, and where the output is a narrative of the issues and the problems faced in solving them. The research groups will be made up of participants previously engaged in the network building (Gojkovic & Chatzimichail, 2017) and in the social dialogue phases (O'Reilly, 2017). Much of the work will involve creative activities by young people in response to a particular question or issue, and once the groups have been formed, the partners will facilitate the process of the groups' activities. As in the previous stage, interaction during the research activities will ideally take place on the platform, though some users may prefer other media. Each group working on a research activity will have a dedicated space on the platform to record and review work progress. This stage will generate quantitative data, narratives, artefacts such as videos, digital stories, publications, music, art, reports, images etc. The outputs of the research activities will be stored in the WYRED platform repository (García-Peñalvo, 2017b; García-Peñalvo & Durán-Escudero, 2017). The partners involved will facilitate the process where necessary and as far as possible, bearing in mind that, as outlined in the guidelines, each group will remain autonomous.

1.1 Aims of the Activity Toolkit

The WYRED Activity toolkit aims to create a stimulating, audience-specific research activity toolkit and to stimulate civic engagement from the target audience through participation in innovative research methods. This process focuses on social dialogue and open research directed by children and young people. The WYRED Activity toolkit is based on generative research approach to investigate and examine issues internationally or locally that concern them in the digital arena.

This toolkit aims to support the participants in their exploratory activities, which in turn will:

- motivate and prepare children and young people to take an active role in policy making and societal developments;
- stimulate civic engagement of children and young people through online participation;

- promote innovative exploratory methods with the active participation of children and young people through the internet and digital technologies;
- engage children and young people to select and curate artefacts of the research process, by guiding them to find practical solutions for specific problems.

The toolkit defines the research methods and the activities involved, and it explains each stage of the process. The WYRED tool kit is designed to give an insight into how to create projects, describe processes and analyse data with a view to seek solutions to a problem. The participants will form into groups to work on the design of their research projects. They will be able to use the activity toolkit as a reference. The research activities of the groups will generate a range of artefacts such as videos, sculptures, publications, music, reports, and images to name but a few. These will be initially stored in the group spaces. These artefacts will be collected and curated in the WYRED knowledge base, which will be a repository of the results and raw data generated by the research processes. They will be made available on the WYRED platform for use by all participants and third parties not currently involved in the project.

2 Generative research

2.1 Definition

The aim of generative research is to provide a definition for a problem, for which a solution is being sought. This requires to collect in-depth data about the target audience, their needs and their aspirations. A well conducted generative research greatly reduces the risk of misunderstanding the actual problem. It is not uncommon for the problem statement to be rephrased, once sufficient research data is available and describes a different situation to what was assumed.

Researchers will typically immerse themselves in the target audience, conducting ethnographic activities, focus groups, interviews and observations, and usability testing. They aim to collect data that will help them understand motivations, behaviours, attitudes, preferences, opinions, feelings, etc. ¹

A detailed insight into different methods of generative research is attached in Annex 1.

¹For some in-depth explanations, see also: <https://www.usertesting.com/blog/2015/12/17/generative-vs-evaluative-research/>

2.2 Step-by-step guide

The following is an indicative guide, by no means exhaustive; a more detailed guide is available in Annex 2. Participants are encouraged to contribute with their experiences to continuously broaden and enrich the guide.

2.2.1 Refine the research question

Drawing on the information gathered through the social dialogues in WP5, the project partners will be able to suggest topics for the exploratory activities to the participants, and to help refining the research question. The research question can then be adjusted as the exploratory activity progresses.

It is crucial that the problem statement implied is contextualised. In other words, the problem statement should be considered within its larger setting (society, geographical location, historic context, etc.). This allows for the specific aspects and complexities of the problem statement to be captured and explained.

In order to refine the research question, it can be useful to work with a mind-map, or to brainstorm, etc. The top two to three items mentioned can then be taken and connected in an initial statement; the statement can then be reviewed independently for further refinement, and the outcomes compared and summarised in a final statement.

Based on the above, a research question could read as follows:

“How can young people who feel disengaged in today’s society, have their voices heard?”

Note that the research question may also be segmented, i.e. addressing both actual and perceived problems. For instance, it could be that young people’s voices are being heard, but they still feel that nobody is listening. This may then require further investigation and potentially further refinement of the question.

2.2.2 Select a research method

Make a selection based on the table shown above under 2.2. For further assistance with the selection process, see also the decision-making table under Annex 2. Please note however that the list is not exhaustive, and other methods are suitable too.

When selecting a method, various variables need to be taken into consideration for a successful implementation (e.g. resources needed, timelines, etc.). The data collection techniques are defined in the next chapter; they go typically hand in hand with the research method. The use of existing networks (WP4) is strongly suggested (e.g. for solidarity projects).

It is important that ethical aspects are taken into consideration too, e.g. ensure to have explicit consent prior to conduct interviews, avoid actual or perceived plagiarism, etc.

2.2.3 Select data collection techniques

Plan a strategy to gather data. Identify who can provide meaningful data, how many people you will study, what individuals you will need to contact, and the support you can expect to obtain from them. Clarify first what type of data you need to collect, whether you are going to focus on quantitative or qualitative data, or on both.

It is helpful to understand the possibilities offered by both forms of data collection.

Mills (2011) has organised quantitative and qualitative sources in three dimensions:

- Experiencing - researchers draw on their own involvement by observing and taking field notes.
- Enquiring - researchers collect new data by asking people for information.
- Examining - researchers use and make records to collect data.

In figure 1 below, the data collection techniques are clustered under 3E's depends on the research types.

Figure 1: Data Collection Tools using the 3E Techniques Source: Adapted from Creswell (2002).

Implementing data collection takes time, especially if you gather multiple sources of information. By linking it to the research on hand, you can determine the most appropriate technique. Bear in mind that your participants may have limited time to complete instruments or engage in interviews. Keeping an accurate record of the information collected, organising it into data files for numeric or thematic analysis, and examining the quality of the information are important steps during the collection of data.

Assign roles and responsibilities; define timelines

Decide who is going to do what, and by when. Identify what the final, desired outcome is going to be (e.g. a fully edited, 3-minute video summarising interviews), and work backwards to identify deadlines.

Be realistic about the implications of your project, incl. time requirement, travel needs, access to resources or infrastructure, access to key stakeholders, costs involved.

2.2.4 Carry out the research

Use the GRIAL platform to document your research, and to share it internally. Document not just the findings, but also the steps taken to gather data. This will make it much easier to identify potential flaws, to let externals verify the veracity of the data collected, and to identify potential similarities across research groups.

Make sure there are regular progress review meetings - these do not need to be lengthy sessions, but the opportunity to identify issues, define corrective action and set revised deadlines, if at all necessary.

2.3 Report out and dissemination

Decide on the format for the report out (to the full project team, to a select critical audience first, with or without external moderation, etc.). It is often useful to report first to a critical friend, to gather useful feedback and to ensure no major issue is being overlooked.

Dissemination will be organised through a collective and synchronised effort by the whole WYRED team. Depending on the format, various channels are to be considered (conferences, newspapers, journals academic papers, social media, etc.). All the WYRED publications will be open access, using either gold open access route, green open access route, or both. The WYRED project supports green the open access route throughout two communities, one in Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/communities/wyred>), one in the GRIAL research group institutional repository (<https://repositorio.grial.eu/handle/grial/723>).

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Open University, <http://www.open.ac.uk/choose/unison/develop/my-skills/self-reflection>

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4 Annexes

4.1 Annex 1 Generative Research Methods and step-by-step guides

The following table is a summary of known generative research methods. Partners are encouraged to add suggestions of their own, incl. an explanation of the method and references to relevant literature.

Generative Research Methods
A. Research projects
<p>Research projects can typically explore under-researched areas, extend a previous study or replicate an existing study in a different setting. In addition, they can also apply and test ideas and methods in a real-world context.</p> <p>To be successful, research projects need to take into consideration two aspects:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provide a systematic approach to increase knowledge; - Use the newly acquired knowledge to define new applications.
<p>Example:</p> <p>Definition and Application in Health Care Informatics</p> <p>Some research in psychology or social sciences analyse the subjective viewpoint of a target group. To this end, they employ what is called the ‘Q Methodology’, also referred to as the systematic study of subjectivity. This approach looks at self-references and considers data within the whole pattern of responses given by individuals. The individuals are the variables, as opposed to settings, tasks, etc. Participants are asked what is meaningful to them through a ‘Q-sort’. The evaluation of the data helps to form groups of individuals who have ranked characteristics in the same order. An important limitation to be taken into account is that this method works best with small, non-representative samples, and therefore replication of the findings can be difficult.</p> <p>A small group of doctors and medical students from the Chicago area were surveyed and asked to rank-order 30 opinion statements about information technologies within the health care workplace. The Q-methodology research technique was employed to structure an opinion typology from their rank-ordered statements. A typology of six opinions was identified in the following groups: Full-Range Adopters; Skills-Concerned Adopters; Technology-Critical Adopters; Independently-Minded and Concerned; Inexperienced and Worried; Business-Minded and Adaptive.</p> <p>The researchers found that it was possible to forecast the likeliness of individuals to adapt information technologies in the health care workplace. The outcomes suggest that Q-methodology could be implemented to individualise and customise their approach to understanding the <i>personality</i> complexities of individuals and their willingness to adopt information technologies within the workplace.</p> <p>https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/pmc/articles/PMC61268/</p> <p>Further reading: Q-methodology: an Overview, https://www.uel.ac.uk/wwwmedia/microsites/riste/Q-methdology-Article.pdf</p> <p>The Frascati Manual, http://www.oecd.org/sti/inno/Frascati-Manual.htm (general information about research projects)</p>

1. Research projects – a step-by-step guide	
1.1. Research and choose your topic	Give yourself ample time to research the topic of interest; 4 weeks is usually a good timeframe, but it will also depend on how much time you can dedicate to it. Formulate a few initial ideas, e.g. <i>'Wealth distribution in my home town'</i> , and then try to identify suitable sources of primary and secondary information.
1.2. Narrow your topic down to sizeable, measurable parts	The topic can be broken down in smaller parts, with each part being potentially the topic of a research; the parts can then be further narrowed down, and combined for the final topic definition. e.g. <i>'Wealth distribution in the Southern District of my home town'</i> , <i>'Manifestations of wealth distribution in my home town'</i> . ➔ <i>'Manifestations of wealth distribution in my neighbourhood'</i>
1.3. Formulate a research question	This is an iterative process, during the research new data may emerge which will cause you to reformulate the research question; e.g. <i>'What is the impact of manifestation of wealth on the perception of my neighbourhood?'</i>
1.4. Review the suggested methods, and choose the most suitable	Read through the suggested research methods, chose the one that you think you like the most and is most suitable for your purpose, and review it with your coordinator.
1.5. Start work	Your work will mainly consist in collecting, comparing, contrasting and triangulating data. Make conscious choices between sources, primary information and literary sources, etc. Always maintain a professional attitude.
1.6. Your equipment	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Pen and Paper 	<p>Yes, these are still the most common tools of a researcher. They are easy to use, non-obtrusive and cheap.</p> <p>Have them always ready, write down any observation but remember – when having an informal conversation with a member of the target group, wait until the end to take any notes.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Digital Voice/Image/Video Recorders 	<p>Most mobile phones will have one. They are useful when recording long answers.</p> <p>However, you must make sure to obtain the explicit consent of your counterpart, and you must be able to guarantee full confidentiality. Do not share recordings with anyone outside the research group, and destroy the recordings after listening (unless you are collecting it as evidence for your journalistic approach, see Table 3).</p>

	<p>Remember that some individuals are less likely to speak freely if they are being recorded.</p> <p>In some cases, these tools can be used as a good ice-breaker, for instance by starting the meeting by playing a known song.</p> <p>Digital cameras in particular are useful to supplement the final report with photographic materials.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Personal computer (laptop, desktop) 	<p>Use computers to organise and manage schedules, to store and exchange files, to run online questionnaires, to do some online research, etc.</p>
1.7. Write your report	<p>Consolidate your data, and summarise it in a narrative style. Use as many photographic props, graphic illustrations and charts to visually enhance the report. Where appropriate, formulate a thesis and justify it with the data you have collected. Remember to always quote your literary sources, and to acknowledge the support of your contributors. Have a critical friend read and proof-read your work before submitting it for publication. You will be surprised how easily typing errors can slip through, and you may also pick up new ideas!</p>

B. Creative projects

Creative projects are similarly set up like research projects, but with the additional focus on collaboration between researchers, and on the creation of original design and artwork.

Example:

Highway planners worked with artists and citizens to solve a road construction dilemma in Danville, Vermont. The small town sits on a major East-West road, and has some of New England’s most spectacular scenery.

The Danville Transportation Enhancement Project was formed for the redevelopment of a portion of U.S. Highway 2 through the town’s village centre. The Danville project needed to find a way to upgrade road conditions and meet federal highway requirements, while respecting the aesthetic, economic, and cultural fabric of the community.

Highway expansion in rural areas can be difficult and controversial. The Vermont Agency of Transportation (VTrans), however, is a national leader in context-sensitive design solutions and public involvement. Vtrans aims to bring communities together early in the planning process to help design environmentally responsible transportation infrastructure that promotes safety and efficiency while preserving the community’s vision of itself.

A local review committee was formed, including a landscape architect and a sculptor. The artists, working closely with engineers and residents, infused the process with creative problem solving. This was done through intensive interaction with the community. The civic engagement process was the most important aspect of the project. It was purposefully inclusive, sensitive, engaging, and ongoing. Having artists, rather than highway engineers, lead the process seemed less threatening to community participants, and they were more effective at devising satisfying alternatives.

Almost as important as the road design, a number of related activities emerged from the community process. They include a student photography project that led to postcards and a Danville calendar. Other students carved stone figures to be embedded along three miles of concrete sidewalk. Youth planted seedlings in the project’s right-of-way, and they designed tile markers, a ceramic playground mural, and clay cutouts of hands to hang in the village green.

<https://www.pps.org/reference/artsprojects/>

Further reading: 5 Hallmarks of a Creative Project,

[http://creativeeducator.tech4learning.com/2012/articles/Creative Projects](http://creativeeducator.tech4learning.com/2012/articles/Creative_Projects)

2. Creative projects – a step-by-step guide	
Specific topic	<p>For this method, the topic of the research must be very narrow, and address a real and present situation. The ideal outcome is a solution to a real problem, or the improvement of an unsatisfactory situation.</p> <p><i>e.g. ‘How can we avoid the divisive effect of wealth manifestations in my neighbourhood?’</i></p>
Collaborate	<p>The problem or the situation you are trying to address is likely to affect many. Therefore, in order to come up with a solution that is supported by many, you ought to collaborate with as many stakeholders as possible.</p> <p>If the number of collaborators is large, you may need to organise groups and sub-groups, each looking at specific topics.</p>
More than a report	<p>The outcome of this project will have to be a tangible and practical solution. More often than not, you will not be able to actually implement the solution, but this is not an issue. As long as you can show that a solution is feasible, you will already have achieved a great result.</p> <p>Produce visually compelling outputs, such as posters, videos, models, technical sheets etc. of your suggested solution. Your report will be the supporting evidence for your output.</p>

C. Journalistic approaches

A journalistic research can be undertaken alone or in a team; it must be guided by the principles of accuracy (get the facts right), impartiality (report without preconceived ideas, serving no interest other than the truth) and accountability (if necessary, admit to errors and correct them). The typical approach is for someone to take on the role of a reporter and conduct primary and secondary research on data, incl. photographic evidence if possible, and then summarise it all in a format accessible to the majority of citizens; there is a great emphasis on narrative skills. Please note that the sources of information should never be mentioned without the explicit consent of the interviewees.

For primary and secondary research, the internet is always an obvious and good place to start. It has a rich variety of information available, and it can provide sparks and inspiration. However, be aware of the limitations:

- It has too much information (as Mitchell Kapor put it: "*Getting information off the internet is like taking a drink from a fire hydrant*");
- The quality and veracity of the information can be debatable;
- If it is on the web, assume everyone already knows – you are not presenting anything new or original.

So the good news is: not everything is on the internet! Either because the information has not been digitised yet (e.g. historical documents, records held in microfiches), is not publicly shared (e.g. sensitive information about legal, economic, civic topics etc.) or has not been gathered yet.

Excellent alternatives or extensions to internet-based research can be:

- Interviews; this is a great method to gather specific, primary data or to get useful indications on where to look further. Make sure you know beforehand what questions you will want to ask, and draft a list of potential interviewees on the subject. Be courteous and flexible when you approach them and, above all, be transparent. Even if you have a dislike for the person you are interviewing, they are still doing you a favour and you may need to get back to them at some stage in time. Be an active listener and open to digressions: often useful information is provided in side conversations.
- Libraries; university libraries and national archives are likely to have access to large databases and archives. Librarians may be able to help with the research or, at the very least, point you in the right direction.
- National agencies likely to hold data you are looking for; this can be very tricky, as depending on the information requested, the agency may not want or may not be allowed to release the information. There are a few ways to petition for the information, and these may vary from country to country (e.g. the Freedom of Information Act in the UK, <https://www.gov.uk/make-a-freedom-of-information-request/the-freedom-of-information-act>)

Example:

The Vlogstar Challenge provides vlogging workshops to young people in London, linked to a competition. It is run by the [Jack Petchey Foundation](#) and supported by YouTube and a London daily newspaper called 'The Evening Standard'. The organisers provide a one-day training sessions for free, providing participants with the skills and confidence to create their own vlogs with their smartphone. The training course also includes aspects on how to build an audience, and a session to discover and articulate what is important to them. <https://www.vlogstarchallenge.com>

N.B. A project like the Vlogstar Challenge would also fit within category 2: Creative projects

Further reading: The elements of journalism

<https://www.americanpressinstitute.org/journalism-essentials/what-is-journalism/elements-journalism/>

3. Journalistic Approaches – a step-by-step guide	
3.1. Before you begin	
A newsworthy topic	<p>Do not look for topics covered by mainstream media. If you do, try to find a particular angle to it, to make the news really ‘new’.</p> <p>Look for places where news is happening: town hall, parliament, police stations, but also in schools, banks, etc.</p> <p>Finally, make sure the topic is close to your heart: you will spend weeks investigating and recording data, and you are more likely to keep your focus if you are working on something which is particularly important to you.</p>
Ethics	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Truth 	The International Federation of Journalists states that the first duty of a journalist is to have “ <i>respect for truth and for the right of the public to truth</i> ”.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Authenticity 	Never plagiarise; do not distort facts, photographs, videos etc.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Human Rights 	Always respect requests of anonymity. If a source asks you for an answer to be ‘ <i>off the record</i> ’, respect the request. Do not slander or otherwise be offensive. Illustrate diversity in all expressions, incl. points of views.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Objectivity 	<p>Distinguish between factual stories and opinions, and label them accordingly.</p> <p>Do not hide or omit information to further support your own agenda.</p> <p>Avoid of any potential conflicts of interest.</p> <p>Do not show preferential treatment any particular group.</p> <p>Stay well clear from gifts in exchange for covering stories in a certain way.</p> <p>Never cross the line between reporting a news story (simply observing, e.g. taking pictures of angry people), and taking any</p>

	action to make a news story more compelling (e.g. asking people to look angry before taking a picture of them).
Responsibility	If you realise you made a mistake when reporting on a story, accept your responsibility, apologise and supply the corrections to the public through your publications. Invite the public to ask you questions about your story, exchange your views and experiences with peers.
3.2. Get to work!	
Collect Interviews	<p>Your main source of data will be conversations with all sorts of stakeholders. Not every conversation will need to be structured like an interview but, if you intend to use the information gained for your research, make sure you tell your counterpart before you start.</p> <p>Speak to decision-makers, to individuals close to decision-makers, to influencers and observers, but also to the '<i>man on the street</i>'. Compare and contrast opinions, and do not shy away from asking awkward questions.</p> <p>Behave professionally, and accept that some interviewees will not like your questions, and that they may tell you so in no uncertain terms.</p>
Write your report	<p>Start writing a report almost immediately. You will not have much to write about at the beginning, but you can still make a start. Keep adding to it as your research progresses, and keep an open mind about the direction of your report. Sometimes you will have to restart your report, or change parts of it as you discover new information and gain new insights – this is normal practice.</p> <p>Write down good, catchy quotes from your interviews. Good quotes are those that grab attention and add width to the story you are telling.</p>
Collect evidence	Record date, time and place of every interview. Try to triangulate information by accessing public archives, by searching through old newspaper articles, etc. Read through statistics and, if you cannot find a useful one, try to build one yourself.

	<p>Use your camera wisely, and collect photographic evidence wherever possible. Video and sound recordings can also be used as evidence, but make sure you have your counterparts explicit consent beforehand.</p>
<p>Craft your lead</p>	<p>Once you feel you have completed the first draft of your report, start writing the lead. Your lead to the story will set the tone, and will grab the attention of the readers. If you lose them with the lead, you lost them forever.</p>
<p>Finish your report</p>	<p>Once you have a solid lead, add the rest of the report you have been putting together. You will need to rework at least some parts of it, to ensure its tone and direction are consistent with the lead. Make sure it is well structured, use paragraphs and chapters as needed.</p> <p>Wherever possible, do offer solutions to a problem statement, or at least do hint to possible solutions. This will add value to your report, as it will be more likely to be perceived as a constructive contribution.</p> <p>You will also need to quote literary sources, and attribute information you have gathered to their sources (unless they have asked you to remain anonymous).</p> <p>If possible and relevant, make a start on a follow-up story. You may or may not wish to announce it yet, but bear in mind that the follow-up story itself may be a newsworthy item.</p>

D. Action research	
<p>Action research is a process of inquiring about problems and taking actions to solve them. It is a concept of research, a framework that encompasses several methods. It deliberately moves beyond knowledge creation and is participatory by nature. It is based on the assumption that knowledge is always gained through action and for action. The goal is to come up with potential solutions that can be implemented step by step.</p>	
<p>Example:</p> <p>The Joy of writing</p> <p>In order to improve literacy skills among his students, a teacher in Virginia started a project to get them more passionate about writing stories. Conscious of the constraints put on every teacher (time, curricular demands, need for differentiation, etc.), he believed that creative writing could be the key to address those constraints whilst also change his students' perceptions about writing. He started quite simply with a questionnaire to draw a picture about their attitudes towards writing. This allowed him to draft different strategies in place to show students how everyone can learn to write creatively, and to stimulate their interest in writing. The document in the link below provides further details.</p> <p>This is a good example of an action research project, as it contains an inquiry part about a problem, and definite actions to solve a problem; it was a participatory project, and worked on the assumption that the skills needed (the knowledge) was going to be gained through action.</p> <p>https://gse.gmu.edu/assets/docs/lmtip/vol1/D.OHalloran.pdf</p> <p>Further reading: Undertaking Action Research http://sru.soc.surrey.ac.uk/SRU34.html</p>	
4. Action Research – a step-by-step guide	
4.1 Before you begin	
<p>Choose a concern</p>	<p>Action research, as suggested by the name, is all about taking action.</p> <p>Identify something that concerns you, and ask yourself: '<i>What do you want to improve?</i>' The answer to this will drive your research, so choose the concern carefully. To get you started, think of one small thing that has an impact your daily life.</p>
<p>Give reasons for your concern</p>	<p>What are the reasons of your concern? It is really important for you to identify the reasons, as they constitute your life values. The project will be more effective if you can uncover the reasons behind your concern, and connect them to your values. The reasons can be anything that is true for you, e.g. you may want to improve the perception of your neighbourhood, because you worry that its unfair reputation holds young people back from a professional career.</p>

Identify potential actions	Make a list of all the ways you might help address your concern, e.g. ways to improve your neighbourhood's reputation. Discuss this with peers, to get a deeper perspective and, potentially, new ideas.
Iterative process	Your actions may or may not work. Even if they work, you may need to go back and adjust them to optimise the outcome, or to get ready to implement a follow-up action. You may also find that some actions are more powerful if run in parallel.
Identify collaborations	Action Research should not be carried out on your own. Identify who could potentially add value to your research. They do not necessarily need to be your friends or share your same opinion, as long as they share the same concern.
Define success	Identify easily verifiable standards that will allow you to see at any time whether you are on track to deliver a successful project, or whether you need to take corrective action. For instance, you may aim to have a feature published in your local newspaper, reporting favourably about your neighbourhood.
4.2 Collecting Data	
Keep a diary	This is the most uncomplicated and immediate way to start collecting data. Bear in mind that every single data you record should be related to what you are trying to identify. Record what you see and experience on a daily basis with regards to your concern, e.g. <i>'Today another shop closed in my neighbourhood'</i> .
Conversations with stakeholders	Hold formal and informal conversations with stakeholders, to widen your horizon, to get a variety of perspectives and to gain a deeper and wider understanding of the situation. You can also use questionnaires, or simple observations.
Read relevant literature	It is unlikely that you are alone with your concerns, and that someone somewhere has not tried something similar before.

	<p>Try also to find out about the structure, feasibility and requirements of your proposed actions.</p>
<p>4.3 Get to work!</p>	
<p>Test out your actions</p>	<p>Start implementing one or two of your proposed actions, e.g. <i>‘Our local radio station will run a feature about the independent stores in my neighbourhood.’</i> Measure the impact, then adjust and repeat the actions if necessary, or start deploying a follow-up action, e.g. <i>‘The independent stores run an open-street market in my neighbourhood, and it is advertised on the radio and in the local newspaper.’</i></p>
<p>Collect evidence</p>	<p>In the meantime, keep recording and highlight any changes you may have noticed.</p> <p><i>e.g. Questionnaires and interviews I ran pre- and post- broadcast of the radio feature show a slight improvement in people’s opinions about my neighbourhood.</i></p> <p>Bear in mind that the above is both data and evidence: it is data because it is information about the perception of your neighbourhood, but it is also evidence as it shows a change in perception. This means that your diary is likely to contain some evidence.</p>
<p>4.4 Analyse your data</p>	
<p>Write a structured report</p>	<p>Introduction: write something about you, your background, your family, etc. This will make it easier for the reader to understand your concern, and the reasons for it, and to empathise with you.</p> <p>Middle section: describe your research story, what happened, what you did, what the stakeholders involved did and what happened. You should include details of your collaborators, other stakeholders that were actively involved, observations, summary of your data collection and your own reflections. You may also include details and excerpts of relevant literature you have read.</p>

	<p>Conclusion: draw conclusions about what has happened, what went well and what did not, how the research might be improved in the future, and what your new knowledge and theory look like at the end of the project.</p>
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E. Solidarity projects	
<p>Solidarity projects seek to promote mutual care and understanding, usually through community-based initiatives targeting underserved groups. With it comes the idea of empowering the target groups, and of building bridges across communities and generations.</p> <p>Solidarity is usually seen as support given by individuals or groups to other individuals or groups, who would not be able to address their basic needs without outside help. It is different from charity since solidarity can also mean mutual support, it is more than just monetary support and it is a long-term, sustained effort intended to empower the receivers to become independent.</p>	
<p>Example: School project in Tanzania, by an Italian non-profit organisation. Funds are raised in Italy, to secure essential schooling in underserved areas of Tanzania. The funds cover access to pre-primary and primary school, incl. a canteen, stationery and books, staff and health provision. Access to schooling is vital in the agricultural areas, as it allows children to gain the necessary skills to contribute to a sustainable economy, but it also allows their parents to focus on their work on the fields. A local committee has been set up to manage the project locally. The local committee comprises the school principals, school co-ordinators, council and parish representatives, as well as parents.</p> <p>The project has recently allowed for a group of children to spend two days in a national park, fully immersed in nature. This is a big step for local children, to be able to go on a school trip in their own country.</p> <p>More information on http://www.nessunoesclusoonlus.it/sad-lugarawa.html</p> <p>Further reading: Emmaus solidarity projects https://www.emmaus.org.uk/solidarity</p>	
5. Solidarity Projects – a step-by-step guide	
5.1 Before you begin - Familiarise yourself with the following key concepts:	
Solidarity	Solidarity is the support given by individuals or groups to other individuals or groups, who would not be able to address their basic needs without outside help. It is different from charity in that solidarity also means mutual support and not just monetary support. It is a long-term, sustained effort intended to empower the receivers to become independent, after which the project may end.
Need for solidarity	No public, private, political or commercial entity can claim to have a one-size-fits-all solution to widespread issues affecting society at large (e.g. unemployment, aging population, widening inequality, growing wealth gap, lack of access to education, lack of representation, ecological destruction, etc.)

	Solidarity can be seen as a powerful tool to address some of those issues, often starting on a small scale.
Plan for the long run	A solidarity project is not really completed until the intended goal has been achieved. Even though you are likely to plan to offer support through a small project, it is likely that the project would take years to complete. Therefore, choose actions that you are sure you can deliver within your given timeframe, state your intentions clearly at the beginning, and explain how far you are prepared to go with the project.
Ethics	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • People-centred 	Solidarity encourages participation from all backgrounds; it values people and celebrates diversity. People’s skills and experiences are key resources for solidarity projects. Solidarity anticipates people’s needs and adapts according to them. It recognises the importance of human feelings.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Inquisitive 	Discover why things are the way they are, and explore their context.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Self-reflection 	This is an integral part of the action taken, and is used to gain insights to inform future actions.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Holistic 	Solidarity links the past, present and future, it connects individuals, groups, society and the environment. It brings local, regional and global realities closer.
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Non-neutrality 	Solidarity projects are not neutral. The reasons and intentions are made clear. Solidarity is transparent about the interests it is trying to serve.
5.2 Identify a cause to support - examples:	
Social movements	Trade unions; support groups for the homeless, the sick, etc.; environmental justice organisations; etc.
Community initiatives	Grassroots development projects; community radio stations; local markets; cultural programmes; etc.

Cooperatives	Cooperatives are voluntary associations to address member needs and are democratically controlled. Cooperatives can engage in various kinds of activities, such as housing, farming, financial services, retail, transport, education and training, arts and culture, manufacturing and even tourism.
5.3 Get to work!	
Conversations with stakeholders	Hold formal and informal conversations with stakeholder who support a cause similar to the one you have chosen. Use the conversations to gain a realistic perspective of the work involved, as well as detailed insights into the processes and resources involved.
Read relevant literature	It is very likely that someone, somewhere has tried something similar before. Find out about the structure, feasibility and requirements of your solidarity project.
Build networks	Solidarity is collaborative and people centred, it relies on people's skills and experience as its main resources. By building networks of interest, you will leverage these resources.
Deliver support	Whatever cause you have chosen to support, use your networks to start delivering your support. Make sure you keep a record of what is being done; this will help you to retrospectively analyse the quality and efficiency of your work, and to draft your final report.
Identify an outlet	You will want society to know about your project. The success of your project may also depend on a widespread support from society. Therefore, you must find an outlet to give your project a voice, a channel through which you can inform the public about your hopes and ambitions, successes and setbacks, requests and offers.

	<p>Make sure your final report is anticipated and broadcast through your main channel.</p> <p>You may want to choose a combination of channels, e.g. social media, print media and radio. Remember however that every channel will require a certain degree of constant attention, and therefore can drain some of your resources. For instance, having a Twitter account is of little use unless new tweets are posted on a regular basis.</p>
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F. Ethnographic projects	
<p>Ethnography is the study of social interactions, behaviours, and perceptions that occur within groups, teams, organisations, and communities. Ethnographic projects aim to acquire the perspective of the target group, as well as the common views of the world surrounding them. This is done through observations and conversations while immersed in the field. Whilst the aim is very much to learn about the target group, there is no intention to influence it.</p>	
<p>Example:</p> <p>Women Leaders as Change Agents</p> <p>This ethnographic study retraces the life of Mary Campbell from Pittsburgh, Pennsylvania. Untypically for her time, she was not raised according to gender biased standards, but was always encouraged to do whatever her brothers did. Mary also received a Catholic upbringing, which instilled in her many of the values she maintains today, such as giving back to her community. A high school service project introduced her to two nuns who had devoted their lives to helping inner-city children. From there on, Mary was inspired to pursue studies in social work, and went on to take on several leadership roles in community work. Through this project, the researcher was able to show how women can be actual agents of change, contrary to some belief that women are simply “cogs in the machine”.</p> <p>http://digitalcommons.iwu.edu/cgi/viewcontent.cgi?article=1017&context=anth_ethno</p> <p>Further reading: http://www.cusag.umd.edu/documents/WorkingPapers/ClassicalEthnoMethods.pdf http://blog.usabilla.com/top-ethnographic-research-videos/</p>	
6. Ethnographic projects	
6.1 Before you begin - Familiarise yourself with the following concepts:	
Cultural interpretation	<p>This is the researcher’s ability to describe things heard and seen within the framework and context of the target group’s view of reality. How do they see it, where do they see it from? The interpretation is based on collected data, using a holistic perspective, placed in a context, and with non-judgemental view of reality.</p>
Holistic and contextualised perspective	<p>Learn to observe beyond the obvious, to see beyond an immediate scene (whether in a shop, in a hall, in a street, etc.).</p> <p>This requires considerable time, and you will formulate various hypotheses to cover all angles (e.g. ‘<i>Why do the neighbours shop in a different neighbourhood?</i>’)</p> <p>This allows to identify the interrelationships among various</p>

	<p>systems in a community. Contextualising means to place observations in a larger perspective.</p>
Non-judgemental	<p>Allow the research to go into any direction. Ensure data are valid, and prevent data contamination. Abstain from inappropriate and unnecessary judgements.</p>
Structure and Function	<p>The social structure is the configuration of the target group, such as kinship (e.g. family) or business structure (hierarchy in an industrial setting). Function refers to the social relations among members of the target group.</p> <p>The data collected in the research allows to understand the structure of the target group, and to retrace the social functions.</p>
Symbols and Rituals	<p>Symbols are the expression of powerful feelings and thoughts (e.g. religious or political symbols).</p> <p>The repeated pattern of symbolic behaviour constitutes a ritual (e.g. religious rituals, graduation rituals at university, etc.)</p>
Ethics	<p>Permission – always request formal permission. Always.</p> <p>Honesty – explain what you want to do, hide nothing.</p> <p>Trust – to be successful, you will need to gain trust of the participants.</p> <p>Pseudonyms – where needed, use pseudonym to disguise personal information.</p> <p>Guilty knowledge – if you gain access to confidential knowledge of illegal or illicit work, step away. Such a situation is unsuitable for this kind of project.</p> <p>Rigorous work – do not falsify nor plagiarise data, always behave professionally.</p>
6.2 Get to work!	
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Selection and Sampling 	<p>The choice of the place and people to observe depends on the research questions. It is crucial that the right choice is made from</p>

	<p>the beginning. Should you notice that you made the wrong choice, take immediate action and start afresh.</p> <p>Make sure you have a short list of what you want to study, and a long list of what you do not want to study. At first, you may be mixing and mingling with everyone and observe them all; as your research progresses, you will narrow your focus to a specific portion of the population, or to just a few individuals.</p> <p>e.g. You may want to start by observing the '<i>Shopping behaviour of people living in my neighbourhood</i>', but then narrow your focus to young people only, and to a specific street only.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fieldwork 	<p>You will be doing lots of fieldwork. Observe, interact and collect data, lots of data!</p> <p>This means you will be working with people for an extended period in natural settings (i.e. out in the real world, not in an interview room or over the phone.) This will prevent you from getting artificial responses, which are typically given in controlled environments. This will also provide a more realistic perspective of the data.</p> <p>The more observations you do, the more likely you are to formulate and ask relevant questions.</p>
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identify an entry point 	<p>You will need to gain access to the entry point. This may be more complicated than you think. Whatever your choice, be aware of its implications.</p> <p>You can get access through the 'right' person, usually a well-known individual with some level of influence. This may be helpful to gain the group's trust, but on the other hand this may also prevent you from accessing some data. A powerful position can cause a block in the flow of some data (e.g. unwelcome news being hidden). For example, you may ask the owner of a shop to observe transactions at the tills. The other only option is to access randomly, which is basically like</p>

	walking into a room of strangers and asking for permission to observe them. In most cases, this is not realistic.
6.3 Collect Data	
Participant Observation	<p>The best way to observe is to participate in the lives of the target group. You must maintain a professional distance and, as a general rule, participation should last at least 6 months. If this is not possible, make sure you mention this limitation in your final report.</p> <p>Strictly speaking, observation without participation is not ethnography, but you can still apply ethnographic methods. Again, if participation is not possible, make sure this is highlighted in the final report.</p>
Conduct interviews	<p>Structured interviews have explicit goals and ask specific questions.</p> <p>Semi-structured interviews are the same as structured ones, except they grant some freedom to digress from the main topic.</p> <p>Informal interviews are a very common technique; similar to casual conversations, this approach allows to discover categories for an implicit research agenda.</p> <p>Independently on the approach you choose, you will have to do some research on interviewing structure and technique.</p>
Questionnaires	<p>Questionnaires are a very formal and rigid way to exchange information.</p> <p>There are many risks associated with this. Individuals may have a distorted image of themselves; in addition, lack of honesty, misunderstanding of the questions etc. can also lead to misinterpretation and/or misrepresentation.</p> <p>If used with the necessary caution, however, online questionnaires are an excellent way to document data quickly, especially for large-scale data collection. Bear in mind though that response rates to online questionnaires are always very low,</p>

	and that equal representation of socio-economic groups is extremely difficult to obtain.
Outcroppings	<p>So-called ‘outcroppings’ are an excellent way to quickly estimate aspects of an area without any human interaction. For example, walking down a street and looking at the different kind of houses and cars parked in front of them can give you a good idea of the wealth of that area.</p> <p>However, it is paramount that each outcropping is placed in context. For example, if there are broken syringes on the pavement, it is sensible to look around before drawing any conclusions (e.g. is it in front of a hospital, or a school?).</p>
6.4 Analyse your data	
Data analysis	<p>An ethnographic research involves many levels of iterative analysis.</p> <p>The analysis helps to test hypotheses. There are various techniques to help you make sense of multitude of data, we have just summarised five of them.</p>
Triangulation	<p>You will have to test a source of information against another source, to strip away alternative explanations. This will also assess the quality of the information, and improve the accuracy of your findings.</p> <p>Triangulation may occur naturally in a conversation. It may also produce conflicting results, which will require you to look for additional data.</p>
Patterns	<p>Patterns are a form of ethnographic reliability. For example, you will start by listing all the data you have on specific behaviours. You will then compare and contrast the data, until you think you can identify a list of behaviours (e.g. you may observe that young people rarely shop in your neighbourhood).</p> <p>You will then go back to observing and listening, and compare your observation with the previous list, until a pattern is detected</p>

	<p>(e.g. you may notice that young people, mainly girls, only shop in your neighbourhood at certain times and days). In practice, this means that you will simultaneously work on many patterns until you are satisfied.</p>
Charts	<p>You can use charts to represent many aspects, e.g. a chart that maps an area/key locations/key events taking place in the area/etc.; a flowchart illustrating processes and activities within the target group; organisational charts displaying hierarchies, dependencies, functions etc., but also change over time.</p>
Matrix	<p>A matrix provides a simple but informative way to compare, cross-reference and contrast data.</p> <p>For example, to analyse news bias, you could analyse a newspaper to measure the length of news stories in words, compare with the frequency of specific key words used, and then record how much time is devoted to the same stories on prime television news slot.</p>
Statistics	<p>Ethnographers can use rather complex statistics. For the purpose of this project, you may want to use two simple methods:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - a pure nominal scale (e.g. There were 24 cars parked on the street we observed, of which 23 had a local registration plate, 4 were Ford cars, etc.; or 89% of the houses had at least one car, 12% had at least two cars, etc.). - a Likert scale, based on answers indicating the level of agreement or disagreement with a statement (e.g. strongly agree, agree, neutral, disagree, strongly disagree); e.g. 33% of the respondents strongly agreed that there are too many cars parked on their street, and 48% said they agreed with the statement, etc.

G. (additional project methods, to be added by partner organisations) ...

Example: ...

7. [project method] – a step-by-step guide

4.2 Annex 2: Decision-making template for the research activity

Main objective: I want to...	Fitting approaches
... increase knowledge on a topic	1, 2, 3, 6
... define or create new solutions, applications, tools, services, etc.	2, 4, 5
... summarise and publicise findings to a wider audience	1, 3, 6
... promote specific actions	3, 4, 5
... to help empower specific target groups	4, 5, 6
... build bridges with specific target groups	4, 5, 6
Main outcome: My work will result in a ...	
... written report, case study, white paper, blog, article, etc.	1, 3
... video, posters, comics, musical, play, etc.	2, 4, 6
... formal or informal organisation delivering specific services, producing work, etc.	4, 5
... official or unofficial action to address a specific situation	4, 5, 6
Collaboration: I will work mainly with ...	
... young people	2, 3, 4, 5
... my fellow researchers	1, 3, 6
... third party institutions	1, 2, 4, 5, 6
Timelines: I need my work to be completed within ...	
... a week	2, 3
... a month	2, 3
... a quarter	1, 3, 4
... a year or longer	1, 4, 5, 6

Impact: I want to impact mainly	
... public opinion	3, 5
... young people's attitudes and behaviours	2, 4
... adults' attitudes and pre-conceptions	1, 2, 3
... policy makers	1, 3, 5, 6

List of approaches:

1. Research projects
2. Creative approach
3. Journalistic approach
4. Action research
5. Solidarity projects
6. Ethnographic projects

4.3 Annex 3: Support template for the research activity

(Adapted from the Points of Light Foundation "Mapping Youth Programs for Youth Involvement" handout)

Refine a Research Question	<i>e.g. Does the echo chamber effect distort our perception of current affairs?</i>
Research Method	<i>e.g. Action Research</i>
Aim of the research	
Data collection tools	<i>e.g. check lists (quantitative); observations/interviews (qualitative)</i>
Duration	
Materials	
HOW	
Step 1 Setting the context	<i>e.g. The internet provides access to a vast amount of all sorts of news; algorithms and news aggregators seem to expose users to selected news stories only, with the risk of providing a distorted picture of current affairs</i>
Step 2 Mapping	<i>e.g.</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - <i>What sites do young people visit, and why?</i> - <i>Which sites do they visit most often?</i> - <i>Which alternative sites can be suggested, to achieve a more balanced exposure to news?</i>
Step 3 Create & Share	<i>e.g. produce an infographic summarising the above</i>
Steps 4 Reflection & discussion	<i>e.g. review data with target group, discuss background information, motivation, etc.; analyse potential action; summarise;</i>
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 01.pdf http://www.theinnovationcenter.org/files/Reflect-and-Improve_Toolkit.pdf
	 Activity Toolkit - Handout example 02.pdf https://www.salto-youth.net/downloads/toolbox_tool_download-file-193/CD%20telling%20it%20like%20it%20is%20peer%20education%20and%20training%20manual.pdf

4.4 Annex 4: Data collection template framework

<i>EXPERIENCING</i>		<i>ENQUIRING</i>		<i>EXAMINING</i>	
Participation	<i>It helps researchers learn the perspectives held by study populations. It always takes place in community settings, in locations believed to have some relevance to the research questions. The researcher engaged in participant observation tries to learn what life is like for an “insider” while remaining, inevitably, an “outsider.”²</i>	Informal Interview	<i>The wording of the questions and topics to be discussed are not predetermined. These types of interviews often occur spontaneously. It can be conducted face-to-face or by telephone.</i>	Archival documents	<i>It is information specifically collected for bureaucratic procedures and the like – applications, reports, etc. Archives are often stored as paper files or on electronic storage – computer disks, CDs, DVDs, etc. If a researcher collects original data, he or she has more control what data are collected³.</i>
Performance & other	<i>Drama, exhibition, and video are imaginative and attractive alternatives to the written word.⁴ These imaginative new approaches can be used to demystify the evaluation process. Using</i>	Structured Formal	<i>Verbally administered questionnaires, in which a list of predetermined questions are asked, with little or no variation and with no scope for follow-up questions to responses</i>	Journals	<i>A journal is a scholarly publication containing articles written by researchers, professors and other experts. Journals focus on a specific discipline or field of study.</i>

² *Qualitative Research Methods: A Data Collector’s Field Guide*

³ <http://ctb.ku.edu/en/table-of-contents/evaluate/evaluate-community-interventions/archival-data/main>

⁴ Curtis, L., J. Springett, and A. Kennedy. 2001. *Evaluation in Urban Settings: the challenge of healthy cities*. In *Evaluation in Health Promotion: principle and perspectives*, edited by I. Rootman and M. Goodstadt: World Health Organization Regional Office for Europe.

	<i>creative arts in evaluation offers opportunities for imaginative ways of understanding programs and creating evaluation knowledge. The creative arts may be used in designing, interpreting, and communicating evaluations.</i>		<i>that warrant further elaboration. They are relatively quick and easy to administer.</i>		<i>Unlike newspapers and magazines, journals are intended for an academic or technical audience, not general readers.⁵ The journal writing is the effective tool to make connections with your knowledge and others.</i>
Story Telling	<i>STORYTELLING is the art in which a teller conveys a message, truths, information, knowledge, or wisdom to an audience – often subliminally – in an entertaining way, using whatever skills, (musical, artistic, creative) or props he chooses, to enhance the audience’s enjoyment, retention and understanding of the message conveyed. Stories are sometimes told purely for joy and delight.⁶ Storytelling can help researcher to experience their research process with enjoy.</i>	Questionnaires	<i>They usually include a set of standardized questions that explore a specific topic and collect information about demographics, opinions, attitudes, or behaviours. They can contain short closed-ended questions (multiple choice) or broad open-ended questions. Questionnaires are used to collect data from a large group of subjects on a specific topic. Currently, many questionnaires are developed and administered online. Three popular programs that allow you to create online surveys</i>	Maps	<i>A map is a symbolic depiction emphasizing relationships between elements of some space, such as objects, regions, or themes. (Wikipedia) Researchers can use maps to collect and present their data more regular.</i>

⁵ University of Victoria, <http://www.uvic.ca/library/research/tips/journal/index.php>

⁶ Berice Dudley, ‘What is Storytelling’, <https://www.australianstorytelling.org.au/storytelling-articles/t-z/what-is-storytelling-berice-dudley>

			are <u>Google Forms, Survey Monkey, and Poll Everywhere</u> .		
Self Reflection	<i>Self-reflection is like looking into a mirror and describing what you see. It is a way of assessing yourself, your ways of working and how you study. To put it simply 'reflection' means to think about something. Reflecting and composing a piece of self-reflective writing is becoming an increasingly important element to any form of study or learning.⁷</i>	Attitude Scales	<i>Attitude scale is a measure or assessment used to assess an attitude - usually for the purpose of comparison.⁸</i>	Audio & Video Tapes	<i>In research process videos can be used in a number of ways such as participatory video, videography, video interviews and elicitation and video based fieldwork. The ability of a video to fix something in its time and its place have an interesting effect in that it can re-awaken the memories and experiences of a researcher or participant. Also, video can support an exploratory research design and extended data</i>

⁷ Open University, <http://www.open.ac.uk/choose/unison/develop/my-skills/self-reflection>

⁸ What is attitude scale? definition of attitude scale (psychology dictionary) <http://psychologydictionary.org/attitude-scale/>

					<i>discovery. It can be 're-opened' for later analysis and capture things not noticed at the time of being present.⁹</i>
Intentional Conversation	<i>Conversation has been seen as a method of research. It can be a research methodology in collaborative action research with sharing of knowledge and the growth of understanding occurs through meaning making process. Conversation occurs between and among people and it is a cooperative venture. New understanding arises through conversation.</i> <i>Conversation help to bring the light thoughts and ideas, facilitate communication with each others, exchange of knowledge and generation of understanding. Also, it helps to make decisions.¹⁰</i>	Standardized Tests	<i>A Standardized test is a test that is given in a consistent or "standard" manner. Standardized tests are designed to have consistent questions, administration procedures, and scoring procedures. Standardized tests come in many forms, such as standardized interviews, questionnaires, or directly administered intelligence tests. The main benefit of standardized tests is they are typically more reliable and valid than non-standardized measures. They often provide some type of</i>	Artefacts	<i>Artefacts means 'an object that is made by a person, such as a tool or a decoration, especially one that is of historical interest'¹² A Research Artefact is an object that serves as a physical (and tangible) visualisation of a set of data values (researcher's ideas, knowledge, information on a subject, wants etc.) that are personal to the researcher. It visualises a data set of the researcher in a form that is meaning full to them.¹³</i>
				Field note	<i>Field notes refer to transcribed notes or the written account derived from data collected during observations and interviews. There are many styles of field notes, but all field notes generally consist of two parts: descriptive in which the</i>

⁹Carey Jewitt, 'An introduction to using video for research' National Centre for Research Methods Working Paper 03/12, Institute of Education, London, March 2012. http://eprints.ncrm.ac.uk/2259/4/NCRM_workingpaper_0312.pdf

¹⁰Allan Fedman, 'Conversation As Methodology in Collaborative Action Research', School of Education University of Massachusetts, <http://people.umass.edu/~afeldman/ActionResearchPapers/Feldman1999.PDF>

¹²Cambridge dictionary. <http://dictionary.cambridge.org/dictionary/english/artefact>

¹³<http://archaids.blogspot.com.tr/2011/11/definition-of-research-artefact.html>

“standard score” which can help interpret how far a child’s score ranges from the average.¹¹

observer attempts to capture a word-picture of the setting, actions and conversations; and reflective in which the observer records thoughts, ideas, questions and concerns based on the observations and interviews. Field notes should be written as soon as possible after the observation and/or interviews.¹⁴

¹¹ Johnson Center, http://www.johnson-center.org/downloads/pdfs/What_is_a_Standardized_Test.pdf

¹⁴ Observation and Field Notes, https://hci.cs.siu.edu/NSF/Files/TeachingPD/How_CI_Observation%20and%20Field%20Notes.pdf

4.5 Annex 5: Intellectual Property and Copyright with Open Access, Creative Commons

Intellectual property is something intangible, and can be referred to as creations of the mind: inventions, literary and artistic works, symbols, names and images used in commerce. Intellectual property is divided into two categories:

- Industrial Property (patents, trademarks, industrial designs, geographical indications);
- Copyright (literary works such as novels, films, music, artistic works such as paintings and sculptures, architectural design, etc.).

Like any property, Intellectual Property can be sold and transferred, and therefore needs protection and management instruments. One of the protection instruments available is the copyright (other examples would be trademarks and patents). A copyright is the legal right given to a third party for a fixed term to print, publish, record, distribute etc. the intellectual property. In commercial settings, copyrights are usually given in exchange for a fee.

The findings of a research are generally considered to be Intellectual Property. To manage the copyright arising from the findings of the WYRED Project, we will consider two main approaches currently in widespread use.

1. Open Access

The practice to allow unrestricted access to research information with limited restrictions on use is called 'Open Access'. This generally means that access is guaranteed free of charge, and typically online; at the same time, information can be freely used but copyright restrictions remain in place. It is important to notice that the practice is initiated by the author, i.e. it is the author who decides how to disseminate the findings. There are actually no legally binding definitions or agreements on what constitutes 'Open Access'; rather, it is based on common practice especially within the EU, and on a 'one size fits all' concept. An in-depth explanation of Open Access in Horizon 2020 can be found here:

<http://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=openaccess>

Open Access remains the preferred method of dissemination for the WYRED Project.

2. Creative Commons

The Creative Commons approach is somewhat similar to Open Access, but with two significant differences:

1. The approach is based on legally binding licenses provided by Creative Commons, a USA-based non-profit organisation. <https://creativecommons.org/>
Since the licenses are based on the US Legal System; to make them applicable around the globe, they have been adapted and released by local offices around the world. Most of the EU states now have

binding Creative Commons licenses available, with the notable exceptions of Hungary, Ireland, Latvia and Lithuania (as of April 2017).

2. Creative Commons provide a range of 4 different licensing types, offering a variation of access and usage rights. This means that access rights can be tailored, according to the needs and expectations of the author:

<https://creativecommons.org/share-your-work/licensing-types-examples/>

4.6 Annex 6: Infographics for young participants

How to get Started

BEGIN

YOUR MOTIVATION

Think about 2-3 things you would like to change, and of people you may want to involve.

REVIEW

Scan through the list of Research Methods, and match them with your motivation to change things...

THE TOOLS

CHOOSE

DISCUSS YOUR CHOICE

Identify 1-2 methods you find most appealing. Discuss them with your Coordinator, to fully appreciate what they entail

GO!

TAKE THE FIRST STEP

Use the step-by-step guide to get started. Give yourself a timeline, and periodically review progress with your Coordinator.

RECORD

Remember to record every step you take, and to write down lots of information. This will make it easier to create the final report, in whichever format you have chosen, and to track back your work, if needed.

RECORD AND REPORT

PUBLISH

PUBLISH YOUR WORK - CONGRATULATIONS: YOU ARE NOW A PUBLISHED AUTHOR!

RESEARCH METHODS

THE TRADITIONAL RESEARCH

Research projects typically explore under-researched areas; they can also replicate an existing study in a different setting. They apply and test ideas in the real world. To be successful, you will need to be systematic, and apply the newly acquired knowledge in the real world.

CREATIVE PROJECTS

Similarly to the traditional research projects, but with particular attention on the collaboration between researchers, and on the creation of original design and artwork.

JOURNALISTIC APPROACH

A journalistic research is undertaken alone or in a team; key to its success are accuracy (get the facts right), impartiality (serve no interest but the truth) and accountability (if necessary, admit to errors and correct them). Take on the role of a reporter and conduct primary and secondary research, incl. photographic evidence. Tell the story so the majority of citizens can read it - your narrative skills will be tested.

ACTION RESEARCH

A process of inquiring about problems and taking actions to solve them. It makes use of several methods and requires participation of many stakeholders. It is based on the assumption that knowledge is always gained through action and for action. The goal is to come up with step by step solutions to existing problems.

SOLIDARITY PROJECTS

Solidarity projects promote mutual care and understanding. They target underserved groups and work with the support of the whole community. The idea is to empower target groups. Solidarity is support given to individuals or groups, who are reliant on outside help. It is different from charity since solidarity means mutual support, not just financial aid, so that the receivers can become self-reliant over time.

ETHNOGRAPHIC PROJECTS

Ethnography is the study of social interactions, behaviours, and perceptions that occur within groups and communities. The aim is to see the surrounding world from eyes of the target group. This is done through observations and conversations while immersed in the field. Ethnographic projects require a great deal of personal involvement, are very time consuming but can also be great fun.

